

SmartCorners

D3.1

Design report on thermal and cabin comfort control

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1 Executive Summary

The market share for battery-electric vehicles (BEVs) is constantly increasing and displacing vehicles powered by a combustion engine. Tough competition in the new market segment is promoting innovation. The propulsion systems are constantly being optimized. Since the energy density of batteries remains the limiting factor for both cost and range, it is of particular importance to improve the performance of the main energy consumers such as the propulsion system, the thermal system (powertrain) and the heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system (cabin). At the same time customer demands for safety, cost, and comfort remain consistently high and continue to drive technological progress forward.

The SmartCorners project aims to significantly improve the holistic thermal management performance. This is done by the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) based control functions to increase energy-efficiency, user comfort and circularity.

The design process of the architecture of a thermal and HVAC system for BEVs is evaluated in in this document. Operating ranges and functional requirements of modern thermal systems are defined. A definition of a state-of-the-art Thermal and HVAC system architecture is done which meets the requirements of modern BEVs' demands. The requirements are compared with the thermal and HVAC system of a demo vehicle (thermal management carrier) and the suitability of the thermal system for use in this project is checked.

Reinforcement learning (RL) models are used to optimize control algorithms based on operating data (vehicle driving characteristics and data on the ambient conditions) to increase comfort and efficiency. The RL models are trained using so-called digital twins. Digital twins are numerical simulations of physical systems, in this case the thermal and HVAC system. Models that accurately describe the operating behaviour of the real system are fundamental for training of RL models. These learn the system responses and define new improved operating strategies.

Digital twins of the thermal architecture and the cabin were created within this project. To improve the prediction accuracy of the cabin model and thus fully exploit the potential of the AI controls, a new method for modelling the cabin is in development. It will be able to use 3D computational fluid dynamics (CFD) data for fast-running models (FRM) to calculate the cabin climate with increased accuracy.

It has been proven that intelligent control has enormous potential. Considering online big data, user characteristics, current and future information on road conditions and current and future weather information can be combined to derive smart control strategies and thus improve the energy-efficiency of heat management systems for electric vehicles (EVs). Furthermore, such self-adaptive software solutions can significantly reduce manual calibration effort on the control systems by human experts, and ultimately, optimize operational robustness in real-world conditions.

The integration of all systems is strengthened in SmartCorners. Additional individual information (on the route, weather and user status, etc.) is made available to the control algorithm in order to derive a holistic and predictive heat management system with improved adaptation to the ambient conditions.

2 Introduction

Holistic thermal and HVAC systems in passenger vehicles is a comprehensive approach that integrates various systems to ensure optimal system efficiency and comfort. This method is particularly crucial for EVs, where managing thermal loads efficiently can significantly impact the vehicle's range and performance rather than the state of health of the battery.

The key components contributing to the objectives related to the thermal management defined in SmartCorners' proposal are:

- Fast-running digital twin of the thermal management system and the cabin comfort (O4.1-O.4.5)
- Integrated predictive user-centric control architecture using reinforcement learning (O4.2-O4.5)

Referring to D1.2 the high-level system architecture of the SmartCorners thermal management system is depicted in Figure 1. The architecture applies to the real vehicle, however, the control unit initially trained in virtual environment. This requires an accurate simulation model of the shown components. Subsequently the control unit will undergo further offline training based on logged data from the real vehicle with real passenger(s) to overcome the inaccuracies related to the unforeseen discrepancies between simulation and real hardware.

Figure 1: High Level System Architecture

The following sections present the process of selecting the architecture of a thermal and HVAC system. This is followed by a detailed summary of modern, state-of-the-art thermal and HVAC systems.

An architecture is derived considering various evaluation factors. A digital twin (O4.1-O4.5) and its operating strategies/modes are presented for the selected design. First, the thermal system is discussed (O4.4), then the cabin model together with the passenger feedback is presented.

This is followed by an introduction to the approach using reinforcement learning (O4.2-O4.5) to upgrade the operating behaviour of the thermal and HVAC system in question.

3 Thermal System Design

The selection of a design for a thermal and HVAC system is individual for each vehicle. For this purpose, requirements are defined from different systems and then transferred to lower system levels. The process is presented below and serves as the basis for the following chapters on selecting the thermal and HVAC system architecture for SmartCorners.

Vehicle development starts with the definition of the attributes. The vehicle class determines the target price for the vehicle and thus also the cost structure for all components in the vehicle. These specifications set initial boundary conditions. The size of the vehicle and the chosen vehicle platform determine the weight and packaging as well as the requirements for the thermal system.

Figure 2 shows the system architecture and how the vehicle requirements are being broken down to the thermal system requirements. Simulation is used at an early stage of concept development to ensure a proper operation of the overall performance. Optimization of the thermal system is done at least on the system level to ensure maximum efficiency. This can be achieved by optimization on a system level.

The range specification, vehicle performance and the charging capabilities impact the selection of technology and components installed in the thermal and HVAC system. The vehicle weight and the desired acceleration capability are translated into a power requirement for the electric machines. Range and estimated performance determine the battery size. The cabin, the inverter and the electric machine are the components with the highest cooling and heating demands and have the greatest influence on the design of the thermal and HVAC system. It is important to consider the maximum cooling and heating capacity and the required temperature levels for the cooling circuits. This is done by setting the peak performance conditions.

Figure 2: Thermal and HVAC System Definition Process

Figure 3 shows a sorting of the different vehicle systems into the corresponding levels. The following test briefly summarizes the processes for each level from the perspective of the thermal and HVAC systems.

Level 0: Requirements related to the vehicle are defined on this level. The vehicle must be capable of cooling the cabin to a desired temperature level via the air conditioning system under very high temperatures and heavy load (high speed). Another requirement is the charging time. The vehicle must reach a certain state of charge within a specified time.

To meet these requirements, different components (e.g., e-machine, HV-battery, inverters and thermal system etc.) must be selected to achieve the target specifications. Based on the technical specifications, the vehicle architecture and the main components are determined. For the thermal system, the type of refrigeration cycle (e.g., heat pump or not). The temperature levels of the components define the number and temperature levels and the number of the cooling circuits. Operating within the respective temperature spectrum is crucial for the performance and lifespan of the component. The spectrum for this is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Vehicle System Level Definition

Level 1: The requirements and technical specifications are transferred to the thermal system at Level 1. Generally, rough heating and cooling demands for the powertrain (HV-battery, e-machine, inverter) and the cabin are already known. From this point, the requirements for the thermal system are broken down to the next level. These include, the temperature at the evaporator outlet.

Figure 4: Comfort Temperature Ranges for Different Vehicle Components

Further requirements and specifications are defined. The following parameter decisions are made:

- What is the max. waste heat produced by the HV-battery, the electric machine, the inverter, and the cabin?
- What is the max. heating demand of the cabin and the HV-battery?
- What is the max. cooling demand for the HV-battery and the cabin?
- Which coolant mass flows are required?
- What heat output is caused by fast charging?
- What are the requirements for defogging and demisting?
- Can the waste heat be used?
- Are there additional interfaces to power electronics?

- What other features are needed for cabin climate control?
- Which cooling technology is sufficient (active/passive cooling or immersion cooling of the e-components)?
- Which coolant is to be used?
- Is an e-heater required?
- Which circuit logic and interconnection are required?

The requirements are translated into technical specifications. It is determined how the components, which need to be heated or cooled, are connected to the cooling system. The necessary functions are defined as follows:

- Heating Cabin (active/passive)
- Heating Components (active/passive)
- Cooling Cabin (active/passive)
- Cooling Components (active/passive)
- Demisting/Defogging (reheat)

The architecture specifies the possible configurations for thermal management to efficiently utilize all energy flows in the vehicle.

Figure 5: Requirements and Technical Specification for a Generic Thermal and HVAC System

Level 2: On this level the requirements for the components of the thermal system are defined. These components include e-heaters, valves, radiators, evaporators, etc. From the previously defined architectures and the totally defined cooling and heating loads, the required volumetric flows for the HV-battery, e-machine and inverter etc. are derived. This is done for

different operating points and environmental conditions. The technical specification on this level includes the maximum allowable pressure losses for the pipes, evaporator and pump etc. Additionally, the design of the components is further detailed, and the performance of the refrigeration cycle is fixed.

Level 3: The thermal system is often divided into subsystems. The refrigeration cycle is one subsystem, the different cooling circuits are another, as well as the cabin conditioning. At this level, a selection decision for the components is made (specific supplier). Data sheets and operating characteristics at different operating points are considered for the selection. Subsequently, the performance (response behaviour, efficiency, etc.) is defined in the technical specification. The interfaces for the functions and interactions of the components are further detailed.

Level 4: At this level, the control strategy for pumps, valves and blowers is made. This is exclusively a software level where the communication between the components and the control unit is elaborated. For the technical specification a software architecture is defined. Furthermore, control and regulation algorithms are programmed. Variables for calibration and expected system responses are documented and can later be used for software calibration and testing.

3.1 Thermal and HVAC System Layout

A thermal system is usually designed according to various specifications. The efficiency of a system is particularly important for BEVs. An EV is much more efficient in terms of the power train; there is significantly less waste heat from the individual components, which can be used, for example, to heat the cabin. In addition, the energy density of a lithium-ion HV-battery, as used in the automotive industry, is significantly lower than that of fossil fuels. In addition, the HV-battery is very temperature sensitive. At low temperatures it loses a lot of usable capacity and the power output drops. This has a major impact on the driving characteristics of the vehicle and the range in wintertime. Both the thermal and HVAC system and the powertrain are powered by the HV-battery. Range and comfort are in direct competition. In addition to selecting the most efficient components possible, the thermal and HVAC system control is important. The operating conditions for the thermal system vary greatly. The environmental condition changes (cool, heat, high and low humidity), the number of passengers changes, the driver's driving style can vary, the solar load changes, to name just a few factors. The control system must be able to react to all changes in the boundary conditions.

In addition to efficiency, comfort is also a factor. Customers have high expectations. A good thermal and HVAC system in terms of comfort is characterized by a quick response, sufficiently high cooling and heating performance and low noise level. Luxury vehicles often have multi-zone automatic climate control. With this, the temperature is regulated in standalone. Up to four different climate zones in the vehicle can be set separately. There are systems that hardly cool convectively; in other systems, comfort is improved by seat and steering wheel heating. New systems have air quality monitoring and automatically introduce fresh air into the vehicle when required. In addition, diverse additional functions are being added, such as a foot warming or foot cooling module or refreshment modes for long journeys, disinfection modes, etc. Other factors to consider when evaluating a thermal system include the cost of a system and its durability.

The use of machine learning (ML) has great potential for optimizing control and thus improving efficiency and comfort. Control functions can be individually and automatically adapted to the environmental conditions, the driver's preferences, etc. for each vehicle separately without hardware changes.

3.1.1 State-of-the-Art Thermal and HVAC System Performance Requirements

In the following chapter, evaluation criteria for thermal systems are presented. An overview of the performance range of current state-of-the-art vehicle thermal management systems is described. Furthermore, other aspects for concept decision (environmental aspects, comfort, comfort feature, costs etc.) are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Evaluation Criteria and Average Performance Parameters for a Thermal and HVAC System

Evaluation criteria	Spectrum of current thermal systems <small>* Power consumption depends on vehicle type and size</small>
1. Thermal Performance	
Interior Warm-Up Time: The time required for the cabin to reach a comfortable temperature. 10-20°C (after 30 Minutes).	Temperature: 10-25°C Power consumption: 4-9kW
Interior Cool-Down Time: The time needed for the temperature to decrease to a desired value 40°C@10 Minutes.	Temperature: 25-40°C Power consumption: 3-6kW
Interior Cool-Down Time: The time needed for the temperature to decrease to a desired value 40°C@30 Minutes.	Temperature: 20-40°C Power consumption: 3-6kW
Compressor Performance: Efficiency and capacity of the compressor for cooling the cabin.	Coefficient of Performance: 2-4 Capacity: 3-10kW
2. Energy Efficiency	
Electrical Energy Consumption by the HVAC System: The amount of electrical energy required for system operation.	Power consumption: 1-3kW
Heat Recovery Efficiency: The level of heat recovery and utilization to support climate control.	50-70% (heat pump)
3. Environmental Impact	
Refrigerant Type and GWP (Global Warming Potential): Assessment of the refrigerant used and its contribution to global warming.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ R-134a and R-1234yf are the dominant refrigerants, ▪ R-744 (CO₂) is considered a promising alternative.
System CO ₂ Emissions: Direct and indirect emissions caused by the system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Direct emissions are caused by refrigerant leaks and depend on the type and quantity of refrigerant used. ▪ Indirect emissions are caused by the energy consumed to power the HVAC system, influencing CO₂ emissions from the vehicle's operation.
4. Performance Under Extreme Conditions	
Operability at Extreme Ambient Temperatures: The system's ability to function under very hot or cold conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High Heat: Systems can handle up to 45-50°C ambient temperatures. ▪ Extreme Cold: Effective heating is expected at temperatures as low as -20°C to -30°C. ▪ Performance varies based on system design, refrigerants used, and technology (e.g., heat pumps in EVs).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operability is judged by the system's ability to maintain comfortable cabin conditions and respond quickly to temperature changes.
Humidity Control and Defrosting Capability: Efficiency in dehumidifying and defrosting windows.	<p>Demisting: 1-3 minutes</p> <p>Defogging: 1-2 minutes</p> <p>Defrosting: 3-5 minutes</p>
5. User Comfort and Convenience	
Air Quality: Efficiency of filters in reducing particles and pollutants, refreshing mode etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Filtration Efficiency: Captures dust, pollen, PM2.5, and some pollutants; high-end systems may include HEPA filters. Activated Carbon: Reduces odors and absorbs harmful gases. Air Quality Monitoring: Automatic adjustments based on external conditions to maintain clean air. Fresh Air and Recirculation Modes: Helps control pollution levels and enhances cabin comfort. Advanced Features: Technologies like ionizers or UV-C light for additional air purification in premium vehicles.
System Noise Level: Noise and vibration levels during operation.	<p>Idle: 30-45 dB</p> <p>High fan speed: 50-60dB</p>
System Response Time: Time taken to detect and adapt to temperature changes.	0.5-2 minutes
Temperature Uniformity in the Cabin: The degree of uniform temperature distribution within the vehicle.	2-3°C
Dynamic Adjustment of Airflows: The ability of the system to adapt airflows based on internal and external conditions.	2-30 seconds
6. Technological Features and Control	
Automatic Interior Temperature Control: Precision and efficiency of automatic control systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Sensors: These sensors are strategically placed throughout the cabin to monitor the interior temperature continuously. Control Panel: The driver or passengers set their desired temperature on the HVAC control panel. Automatic Adjustments: The system uses the data from the sensors to automatically adjust the airflow, fan speed, and the mix of hot and cold air to maintain the set temperature. Comfort and Efficiency: This automation ensures a consistent and comfortable cabin environment, improving both comfort and energy efficiency
Integration with Driver Assistance Systems: Capability to adapt and work with other intelligent vehicle systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptive Climate Control: The HVAC system can adjust temperature and airflow based on data from ADAS sensors, such as those monitoring external weather conditions or the number of passengers. Energy Efficiency: Integration with systems like Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC) allows the HVAC system to optimize energy use by adjusting settings during different driving conditions, such as stop-and-go traffic or highway cruising. Enhanced Safety: By working with sensors and cameras, the HVAC system can improve visibility. For example, it can automatically defog windows when the ADAS detects reduced visibility. Personalized Comfort: The system can use data from driver monitoring systems to adjust settings based on individual preferences, ensuring a more personalized and comfortable driving experience. Predictive Maintenance: Integration with vehicle diagnostics can help predict and alert drivers to potential HVAC system issues before they become serious problems.
Manual and Automatic Control Options: User-friendliness and availability of different control options.	<p><u>Manual Control Options</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Adjustment: Users can manually set the desired temperature using knobs, buttons, or touchscreens.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fan Speed Control: Allows users to adjust the airflow intensity to their preference. ▪ Airflow Direction: Users can manually direct the airflow to different zones such as the windshield, face, or feet. ▪ Recirculation Mode: Manually switch between recirculating the cabin air and bringing in fresh air from outside. <p><u>Automatic Control Options</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Automatic Climate Control: Maintains a set temperature by automatically adjusting the fan speed, airflow direction, and temperature mix. ▪ Dual-Zone or Multi-Zone Control: Allows different temperature settings for different areas of the vehicle, such as the driver and passenger sides. ▪ Humidity Control: Automatically adjusts settings to maintain optimal humidity levels inside the cabin. ▪ Defogging and Defrosting: Automatically activate to clear the windshield and windows when sensors detect fogging or frost. ▪ Integration with Other Systems: Works with driver assistance systems to optimize comfort and safety, such as adjusting settings based on external weather conditions or the number of passengers.
7. Cost and Maintenance	
<p>Maintenance Friendliness:</p> <p>Effort and cost for maintaining and replacing components.</p>	<p><u>Maintenance Friendliness</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modular Design: Many modern HVAC systems use a modular design, allowing for easier access and replacement of individual components such as filters, compressors, and evaporators. ▪ Diagnostic Tools: Advanced diagnostic tools and onboard diagnostics (OBD) systems help quickly identify issues, reducing the time and cost associated with troubleshooting. ▪ Standardized Parts: Using standardized parts across different models and brands can simplify the maintenance process and reduce costs. ▪ Accessibility: Components are often placed in accessible locations to facilitate quicker repairs and replacements, minimizing labor costs. ▪ Preventive Maintenance: Regular maintenance schedules and easy access to service points help prevent major failures and extend the lifespan of the system. <p><u>Cost Considerations</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initial Cost vs. Long-term Savings: While some HVAC systems might have a higher initial cost, their efficient design and ease of maintenance can lead to long-term savings. ▪ Replacement Parts: The availability and cost of replacement parts can vary, but systems designed with common parts tend to be more cost-effective. ▪ Labor Costs: Easier access and modular components can significantly reduce labor costs associated with repairs and maintenance.
<p>Lifecycle Costs of the System: Total costs for operation, maintenance, and replacement over the system's lifespan.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initial Cost: The initial cost of an automotive HVAC system can range from 500-2.000€ depending on the complexity and features of the system. ▪ Operating Costs: These include the energy consumption of the system, which can be influenced by factors like driving conditions and climate. On average, the annual operating cost can be around 100-3000€. ▪ Maintenance Costs: Regular maintenance, including filter replacements, refrigerant refills, and general servicing, can cost approximately 50-150€/year. ▪ Replacement Costs: Major components like compressors or evaporators may need replacement over the vehicle's lifespan. These costs can range from 200-1.000€ per component. ▪ Total Lifecycle Cost: Over a typical vehicle lifespan of 10-15 years, the total lifecycle cost for an automotive HVAC system can range from 1.500-5.000€.

8. Safety	
<p>System Stability and Fault Tolerance:</p> <p>The system's ability to operate stably under load and respond safely to malfunctions.</p>	<p><u>System Stability</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consistent Performance: The HVAC system should maintain consistent performance under different load conditions, such as varying temperatures and humidity levels inside and outside the vehicle. ▪ Robust Control Algorithms: Advanced control algorithms help manage the system's response to changes in environmental conditions, ensuring stable operation without frequent manual adjustments. ▪ Thermal Management: Effective thermal management is crucial to prevent overheating and ensure the system operates within safe temperature ranges. <p><u>Fault Tolerance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fail-Safe Mechanisms: The system should have fail-safe mechanisms that allow it to enter a safe state in case of critical failures, preventing further damage or safety hazards. ▪ Redundancy: Incorporating redundant components and systems can help maintain functionality even if one part fails. This is particularly important for critical components like sensors and controllers. ▪ Diagnostic Capabilities: Built-in diagnostic tools can detect and isolate faults quickly, allowing for timely repairs and minimizing downtime.

3.1.2 SmartCorners Thermal and HVAC System

3.1.2.1 Thermal Management Architecture Evaluation

At the beginning of this chapter, architectural features of current state of the art thermal and HVAC systems are presented. These features are compared with the thermal and HVAC systems of the demo vehicle to ensure/prove its state-of-the-art technology and the suitability of it as a reference for performance for further optimization of the control function on this hardware.

An average automotive thermal and HVAC system for BEVs incorporates several advanced features to ensure efficient thermal and HVAC management. The major operation conditions are listed in the first column of Table 2: Selection Criteria/Desing Decision A rough description of the functionalities is listed in column 2. In Column 3, a check is carried out on the existence of the functions previously designated as state in the thermal architecture of the demo vehicle.

Table 2: Selection Criteria/Desing Decision

	State of the Art Functionality	Used Thermal and HVAC Architecture
Direct Cooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Cooling: Involves cooling the battery directly using a coolant that circulates through for example the high voltage (HV) battery pack. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct cooling of cabin via refrigerant circuit possible.
Indirect Cooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indirect Cooling: Uses a secondary loop where the coolant first cools a heat exchanger, which then cools for example the HV battery indirectly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indirect cooling via LT circuit possible.
Direct Heating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Heating: Involves heating the battery directly using a coolant that circulates through for example the HV battery pack. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct heating via HT and positive temperature coefficient (PTC) heater.
Indirect Heating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indirect Heating: Uses a secondary loop where the coolant first heats a heat exchanger, which then cools for example the HV battery indirectly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indirect heating via medium-temperature (MT) circuit and waste anergy usage.
Refrigerant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R-1234yf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R-1234yf
Number of Coolant Circuits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multiple Coolant Circuits: Typically, BEVs have at least two coolant circuits—one for the high-temperature (HT) components like the e-drive and another for the low-temperature (LT) components like the HV battery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The demo vehicle has a LT, a medium – temperature (MT) and a HT circuit. The battery can operate in a recalculation mode as well.
Chiller Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chiller Integration: The HV battery can operate via a chiller to maintain optimal temperatures. It can also bypass the chiller in a short circuit mode when cooling is not required. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Both option possible in the demo vehicle thermal management system.
System Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key Components: The system includes the HV battery, the e-drive, two coolant pumps, an expansion tank, a radiator, and a refrigerant chiller. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1x Compressor (R-1234yf) 1x Accumulator 1x Chiller 1x iCond (heat exchanger) 1x Evaporator 2x Expansion Valve 1x HVAC Blower 1x Fan 4 x Pumps 4x Liquid/Air Radiator 1x Liquid/Liquid Heat Exchanger 2x Expansion Tank 9x 3/2 Valves
Heat Transfer Capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat from the e-drive (HT) can be transferred directly to the HV battery (LT). Heat can be transferred to the refrigerant via the chiller. Heat can be dissipated to the ambient environment via the radiator. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat from the e-drive (MT) can be transferred directly to the HV battery (LT). Heat can be transferred to the refrigerant via the chiller. Heat can be dissipated to the ambient environment via the radiator.
Waste Heat Utilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste Heat Management: The system can use the waste heat from the e-drive to warm up the battery. The chiller can be used to cool the battery during HT conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The system can use the waste heat from the e-drive to warm up the cabin or battery. The chiller can be used to cool the battery during HT conditions.

The new AI bases control strategy will be tested and validated within a vehicle. For this, important functions were defined as “state of the art” and “must have” for a modern thermal and HVAC system. The Mercedes Benz B-Klass was chosen as the demonstrator vehicle, the vehicle thermal and HVAC system represents all state-of-the-art feature which are currently on the market. The next chapter describes the vehicle.

3.1.2.2 Demo Vehicle

The electrical variant of the Mercedes Benz B Class, see Figure 6, was used as the basis for the thermal management architecture and for the simulation model. The exact specifications are summarized in Table 3: B-Class Vehicle Data. The vehicle's control system was replaced by the AVL control strategy. This will serve as a reference, the vehicle is intended to be used as a test vehicle and for road measurements in the further course of the project.

Figure 6: AVL Prototype Vehicle „Mercedes Benz B-Class“

Table 3: B-Class Vehicle Data

Curb weight	1798 kg	Drive	FWD
Gross weight	2170 kg	Transmission	Single-Speed
Length	4393 mm	Electric Range	200 km
Height	1557 mm	Battery	Lithium-ion, 28 kWh netto
Width	1786 mm	Battery weight	325 kg
Power	132 kW	Charging Power	AC 2.3 – 11 kW
Torque	340 Nm		

3.1.2.3 Thermal Management Hardware Architecture Description

The thermal and HVAC system layout of the demo vehicle has a R290 and a R1234yf refrigerant circuit and a coolant circuit. The demo vehicle can operate with both refrigerants but in SmartCorners only R1234yf is used. The second refrigerant cycle is not relevant for this project and will not be used. Figure 7 shows the highly flexible thermal management architecture. The refrigerant circuits are indicated in green colour, the low-temperature circuit (LT-circuit) in blue colour, the medium-temperature circuit (MT-circuit) in yellow colour, the high-temperature circuit (HT-circuit) in red colour, and the battery circuit (Bat-circuit) in grey colour. Connection pipes between the Bat-circuit and the other circuits are shown in purple.

Figure 7: Thermal Management Layout (demo vehicle)

In Figure 7 each main component or subsystem, such as the HV-battery, e-drive, and cabin, can be heated or cooled. Complexity in this thermal management system is implemented in the coolant circuit, while the refrigerant cycle remains relatively simple. By controlling the valves in the coolant circuit, nine different circuit configurations can be generated. These configurations are divided into the main modes of heating, cooling, and reheat, in relation to the cabin. Depending on the needs of the components, the HT-circuit, LT-circuit, and Bat-circuit can be connected or separated. The MT-circuit is separated and cools the e-drive if necessary or can be used as a heat source via the liquid/liquid heat exchanger. Cooling the cabin via the evaporator or functioning as a heat pump are the main tasks of the refrigerant cycle. As a heat pump, the refrigerant circuit transfers heat from the chiller in the LT-circuit to the iCond (a heat exchanger) in the HT-circuit.

In heating mode, both the cabin and the HV-battery can be heated. The coolant flow of the HT-circuit is isolated and flows through the pump, iCond, e-heater, and cabin heater. If the HV-battery also needs heating, the battery circuit can be connected in parallel to the cabin heater. The LT-circuit connects to the main radiator package. Approximately 14 kW is the maximum heating power of the system, consisting of a 6 kW output from the e-heater and an additional 8 kW from waste heat in the refrigeration cycle. Compressor power and absorbed heat from the environment, the e-drive, and the battery compose the waste heat in the refrigeration cycle.

Reheat mode is very similar to heating mode. The only difference is that the evaporator in the refrigerant circuit is also active. Cabin supply air in the HVAC unit is cooled down and then heated up again before entering the cabin. Cooling the air removes moisture, allowing control of the relative humidity in the cabin. This prevents the windows in the vehicle cabin from fogging up and increases comfort.

In cooling mode, the supply air to the cabin is cooled by the evaporator in the refrigerant circuit. Around 4 kW is the maximum cooling power in the evaporator. The configuration of the coolant circuits depends on the cooling requirements of the HV-battery. For moderate ambient temperatures and low battery loads, passive cooling should be possible. Passive cooling means that the Bat-circuit is connected to the HT-circuit. Coolant flows through the HV-battery, iCond, and main radiator, absorbing waste heat in the HV-battery and iCond and dissipating it to the air in the main radiator. Up to 2 kW is the maximum HV-battery cooling power in this configuration, depending on the ambient temperature and air mass flow through the radiator package. If passive cooling is not possible, active cooling can be used. In this situation, the LT-circuit and Bat-circuit are connected. Coolant absorbs waste heat from the HV-battery, which is transferred to the refrigerant circuit in the chiller. The HT-circuit connects to the main radiator package. Flow goes through the pump, iCond, and then to the radiators. In the iCond, waste heat from the refrigerant circuit is transferred to the coolant, which is then dissipated to the air in the radiator. Depending on ambient conditions, around 5 kW is the maximum HV-battery cooling power.

A physical model was created of the thermal system (the digital twin). In this model, all pipes were represented as 1D models, and the respective losses and transient effects were taken into account. All other components were implemented as 0D sub-models. The characteristic maps of those 0D sub-models are stored here in the form of tables.

3.2 Cabin Model and Passenger Feedback

In SmartCorners the initial training of the user-centric novel control algorithm takes place in a virtual environment. In Figure 8 the interaction between the cabin model and the virtual passenger is shown. The cabin model is fed with the signals from the physical model of the thermal system.

Figure 8: Digital Twin of Cabin with Passenger Feedback

The cabin model provides the comfort rating of the passenger(s). Additionally, to that a measured control signal, for instance, the cabin temperature is compared to the modelled cabin temperature leading to a feedback loop. This generic comfort rating must be personalized considering different user preferences. According to the user-centric comfort ratings a reaction is generated. This deviation can be an adjustment of the set temperature, a change in the flow distribution inside the cabin, or an increment of the blower speed. The deviation signal is then transferred to the control layer. Vehicle cabin models are essential tools

used to assess and predict the thermal state, ensuring optimal comfort under various conditions. In the following some of the available thermal cabin comfort management concepts are shortly described.

3.2.1 Single-Zone Model

The simplest approach is based on a Single-Zone-Model. This model treats the entire cabin as a single, uniform thermal zone, simplifying the analysis and making it easier to predict and control the thermal environment. Single zone models assume that the temperature, humidity, and air velocity are uniform throughout the whole cabin. It focuses on achieving a thermal balance between the heat generated inside the cabin (from occupants, electronic devices, etc.) and the heat exchanged with the external environment (through windows, doors, and the HVAC system). The thermodynamic system boundaries are depicted in Figure 9. The inputs required for single zone models are relatively straightforward, including:

- **Air Temperature:** The average temperature within the cabin.
- **Humidity:** The average humidity level.
- **Air Velocity:** The speed of air movement within the cabin.
- **Radiant Properties:** Solar, background and body radiation, the average temperature of surfaces inside the cabin.
- **Ambient Conditions:** ambient temperatures, vehicle speed.

Single-Zone-Models do not account for variations in temperature and airflow within different parts of the cabin, which can be significant in larger vehicles or under varying external conditions. Additionally, they do not accurately capture the transient thermal behaviour of the cabin, such as rapid changes in temperature. However, a Single-Zone-Model of the cabin model is a valuable tool in the early stages of vehicle design and for basic thermal assessments.

Figure 9: System Boundaries for Cabin Model

3.2.2 Multi-Zone-Model

A Multi-Zone-Model is a more advanced approach to assessing the thermal state within a vehicle cabin. It divides the cabin into several distinct zones, such as the front and rear seats, driver and passenger sides, and even specific areas like the dashboard and footwells. Each zone can have different temperatures, humidity levels, and air velocities. This model accounts

for the interactions between different zones, including heat transfer through conduction, convection, and radiation. This helps in understanding how changes in one zone affect the others. It requires more detailed inputs, such as:

- **Zone-specific Temperatures:** Individual temperatures for each zone.
- **Airflow Patterns:** Detailed airflow distribution within the cabin.
- **Radiant Heat Sources:** Specific radiant heat contributions from surfaces like windows and dashboards.

Multi-Zone-Models are more complex and require more development time and detailed data of the cabin. The demand of computational power and time to run simulations compared to a Single-Zone-Model is larger. However, it offers a higher level of precision in predicting and controlling the thermal environment. At the same time, it allows for customized climate control settings for different occupants, enhancing passenger comfort.

3.2.3 3D-CFD-based Model

A 3D (CFD)-based cabin model is an advanced method used to simulate and analyse the thermal environment within a vehicle cabin. This model provides a detailed, three-dimensional representation of airflow patterns, heat transfer, and thermal distribution.

A 3D-CFD-based model uses precise geometric representations of the vehicle cabin, including seats, dashboards, windows, and other components. It can simulate complex airflows, including turbulence and recirculation zones, the model is able to analyse heat transfer through conduction, convection, and radiation, and can identify local temperature inequalities. 3D-CFD-based cabin models require significantly higher computational power and time for computing. The possibility of coupling such a simulation with system-level tools allows for the most comprehensive approach to thermal management and cabin comfort.

3.2.4 Passenger Comfort Models

Passenger thermal comfort models are essential for designing vehicle cabins that ensure a comfortable environment for occupants. These models consider various factors such as air temperature, humidity, air velocity, and radiant temperature, as well as personal factors like clothing insulation and metabolic rate. The state-of-the-art passenger thermal comfort models are evolving to address the complexities of vehicle environments. By integrating advanced simulations, real-world data, and intelligent systems, these models can enhance passenger comfort while optimizing energy use. Some of the available thermal comfort models are shortly described in the following subchapters.

3.2.4.1 Fanger's PMV-PPD Model

The Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) is a widely used index in thermal comfort studies, developed by Danish scientist P.O. Fanger in the 1970s. This model predicts the average thermal sensation on a scale from -3 (cold) to +3 (hot), with 0 representing a neutral feeling.

PMV reflects the average subjective judgement of a larger group of people who were asked about their feeling of comfort while wearing the same clothing and doing the same activity in the same environment. The factors influencing this perception include the level of activity, thermal resistance of the clothing, room air temperature, average radiant temperature of the

surfaces surrounding the room, air velocity and humidity. ISO 7730 (ISO, ISO.org, 2023) provides the formula for calculating PMV for a specified condition.

PMV allows the prediction of the thermal sensation. To get a more holistic idea of the level of satisfaction of the occupant in the given space, Fanger developed another equation to relate the PMV to the predicted percentage of dissatisfied (PPD).

PPD essentially gives the percentage of people predicted to experience local discomfort. The main factors causing local discomfort are unwanted cooling or heating of an occupant's body. Common contributing factors are drafts, abnormally high vertical temperature differences between the ankles and head, and/or floor temperature. PPD can be calculated with the empirical Formula developed by Fanger:

$$PPD = 100 - 95e^{(-0.03353*PVM^4 - 0.2179*PVM^2)}$$

In Figure 10 below the PPD index at given PVM levels are shown. It assumes that even at neutral comfort feeling there are people who feel dissatisfied.

Figure 10: PPD-Index

3.2.4.2 EHT Model

This model calculates an equivalent homogeneous temperature (EHT) that combines air temperature, mean radiant temperature, and air velocity into a single value. It provides a more comprehensive measure of thermal comfort compared to using air temperature alone. It is particularly useful for assessing thermal comfort in non-uniform environments like vehicle cabins.

The EHT corresponds to the wall temperature of a uniform enclosure with calibrated conditions. These calibrated conditions assume that the average radiation temperature is equal to the air temperature, the air velocity is zero, and the heat exchange between the person and the environment due to convection and radiation is equal to the actual heat exchange under non-uniform conditions. The dry heat exchange and EHT will be the same in both the calibrated and real environments. The EHT allows quantification of heat exchange: high EHTs indicate lower heat loss and low EHTs indicate higher heat loss.

The EHT, T_{eq} , can be determined with the following formulas:

$$T_{eq} = T_s + \frac{x_0}{2x_1} - \frac{\sqrt{x_0^2 + 4x_1\dot{Q}}}{2x_1} \text{ and } T_{eq} = T_s - \frac{x_0}{2x_1} + \frac{\sqrt{x_0^2 + 4x_1\dot{Q}}}{2x_1} \text{ if } \dot{Q} > 0 \text{ and } \dot{Q} < 0 \text{ respectively.}$$

Where is \dot{Q} the heat flux on the manikin surface and T_s is the skin temperature. The constants x_0 and x_1 are evaluated after a linear regression by running calibration simulations in standard

uniform steady conditions at various $T_{eq} - T_s$ conditions (Rommelfanger, Fischer, Frisch, & van Treeck, 2021).

The EHT is incorporated into the ISO 14505 (ISO, ISO Online Browsing Platform, 2006) standard for the evaluation of thermal environments in vehicles or any confined spaces with asymmetric climatic conditions that are close to thermal neutrality. The EHT model uses thermal manikins to represent human bodies, which are subdivided into 17 segments. In Figure 11 on the left hand side the 17 segments are shown, and on the right-hand side a typical plot representation of the results is given. Based on the information gained the flow pattern and temperature distribution can be optimized to enhance the passenger comfort.

Figure 11: Body segments for EHT model and a typical result

3.2.5 Cabin Model Selection

In SmartCorners the employed cabin models have their relevance according to the project phase. The complexity of the cabin model and the comfort model will be gradually increased with the duration of the project. The planned project flow is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Complexity of Cabin Models

A Single-Zone-Model is used at the very early phase, when the toolchain of the thermal-comfort and the RL-based control algorithm is initially developed, providing a foundation upon which more complex, Multi-Zone-Models can be implemented.

As the second stage a Multi-Zone-Approach will be implemented into the toolchain. The thermal comfort prediction is based on the above-described Fanger’s PMV method. The model provides local comfort ratings of legs, arms, chest, and head for all integrated passengers.

As the ultimate step a 3D-based approach will be included into the thermal management system. The comfort rating provided includes the 17 above-described body parts. To overcome the drawback of the increased computational power a fast-running model (FRM) will be derived. FRM is a pure mathematical representation of a 3D-system. This can be done with the help of front-loaded Desing of Experiment (DoE) study, where the input parameter space is scanned through a series of 3D simulations. The output of the study in subsequently feed to a tool (for instance AVL-CAMEO) to create a quick real-time capable digital twin of the cabin. The development process will be described in Task 1.3 and reported in Deliverable D1.3 of SmartCorners.

Table 4 includes input and output signals for the described cabin models. The signals are used to link the cabin sub-model to the thermal management model.

Table 4: Interfaces of the cabin models

Single-Zone-Model	
Inputs	Outputs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar_Radiation (solar radiation intensity and related heat up) T_Amb: Ambient Temperature. V_Vehicle: Vehicle speed. Num_Passangers: Number of passengers. Air_HVAC_IN: Air conditioner input air steam. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Humidity ratio, Mass Flow, Temperature Q_auxilliary: Additional heat from electrical devices. HTC_Amb_vec: Heat transfer coefficients between the surfaces and the ambient air. HTC_Inside_vec: Heat transfer coefficients between the surfaces and the cabin air. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_Cabin_Air: Cabin mean air temperature. T_Surfaces_Inside: Inner temperatures of surfaces (windows, doors....). T_Surfaces_Outside: Outer temperatures of surfaces (windows, doors....). Relative_Humidity: Relative humidity of the cabin air.
Multi-Zone-Model	
Additional Inputs to Single-Zone-Model	Changed/Additional Outputs to Single-Zone-model
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .V_Air Air’s velocity by the surfaces. AirFlowInConfig: From blower to air zone. Blower configuration matrix, it contains the connection between the mass flows from blowers and the air zones. Mass_Flow_Matrix: From air zone to air zone (From-Row, To-Column). Contains the mass flow values between the air cells. This matrix is an input, because the distribution can change with different AC air flow rates. Num_Passengers: Now a vector with a number for each air zone. Q_auxilliary: Now a vector with a number for each air zone. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_Cabin_Air: Cabin mean air zone temperature vector. Relative_Humidity: Relative humidity of the cabin air zones (vector). X [kg/kg] (water mass/air mass): Humidity ratio of the cabin air zones (vector). Local Comfort: {Legs, Arms, Chest, Head} It is a vector which contains the PVM value of the body parts.
3D -Based Model	
Inputs	Outputs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar_Radiation T_Amb: Ambient Temperature. V_Vehicle: Vehicle speed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_Cabin_Air: Cabin mean air temperature. T_Surfaces_Inside: Inner temperatures of surfaces (windows, doors....).

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Num_Passangers: Number of passengers.• Air_HVAC_IN: Air conditioner input air steam.<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Mass Flow, Temperature, Flow distribution• Q_auxilliary: Additional heat from electrical devices.• Recirculation: Air is recirculated in the cabin.• Passenger activity level: 1 --> sitting; 6-10 --> Sports.• Clothing: Summer or Winter.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• EHT: Equivalent homogeneous temperature for all passengers for 17 body parts.
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3.2.6 Passenger Feedback

As mentioned in chapter 3.2 in simulation environment the individual user preferences and reactions must be modelled to ensure that the control algorithm is able to adapt to various users. The personalization block in Figure 8 contains a simple transformation of the standard values regarding the perceptions of cold, hot, neutral, etc. and EHTs, see also Figure 11 right hand side. Some users might prefer warmer air near the legs, others prefer colder air on vicinity of the head, etc. The reaction model is based on the comparison of the actual comfort rating and the neutral perception, indicated as green straight line in Figure 11 right hand side. The difference gives an indication if an overall temperature adjustment would improve the thermal comfort. Changing the flow pattern by mass flow adjustment of the individual air vents can be beneficial to equalize the thermal sensations between different body parts. The reaction model developed in SmartCorners must be able to provide information for the control unit to improve the user-centric comfort.

4 Thermal System Software (Control Layer) Architecture

The goal of the control logic is to operate the components in their comfort zones. An appropriate temperature level is ensured to prevent overheating and damage to the components. Different components have specific thermal operating ranges in which they work efficiently and have maximum life span. The control of the actuators aims to set these ranges.

4.1 Thermal Management Operating Strategy

The Thermal and HVAC control system used in this project has been developed by AVL. It is built up in Matlab/Simulink and it is designed to be used for the physical simulation model of the demo vehicle. The model can be expanded to include vehicle system variables and can also be used in the future to control the thermal system in the vehicle. Figure 13 shows the overview of the software system architecture. The model is divided into a system block (either the simulation model or the signals of the actual thermal system from the vehicle can be used) and the control block. The control block consists of three sub-blocks, the Evaluation-Matrix, State Machine, and Control Algorithm.

Figure 13: Thermal Management System Software Architecture Overview

Evaluation Matrix: The evaluation matrix exports a variable, namely command variable (CV), under the consideration of cabin temperature, the desired cabin temperature, and the ambient temperature. The value of the variable is between the limits -100 and 100, where -100 means highest cooling requirement and 100 highest heating requirements for the cabin. The calculation method is shown in Figure 14.

As a first step the cabin interface temperature, from the human machine interface (HMI) is taken and is scaled to a non-linearized setpoint where changes on the minimum and maximum of the range have a bigger impact on the setpoint than the ones in the middle. In the next step the Pre Command Variable (PCV) is calculated. The PCV is dependent on the ambient temperature and the difference between the actual temperature of the cabin and the desired

non-linearized setpoint calculated by the driver input. In the last step the PCV and the cabin interface temperature is used to generate the PCV value.

State Machine: Inputs for the state machine are the ambient temperature, coolant temperature after the HV-battery, coolant temperature after the HT-Radiator, the CV value and the cabin humidity. Based on those inputs the state machine selects the right state (operation mode).

Control Algorithm: Depending on the state, different control algorithms can be selected. In the simulation, the actuator signals are passed from the control algorithm to the simulation model. The inputs for the control algorithm and the state machine, such as temperatures, pressures and humidities, are fed back from the physical thermal management system.

NON-Linearization		setup control panel (T Cabin Interface)												
		16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
Non-Lin Setpoint		10	13	16	18	19,5	21	22	23	24,5	26	28	31	34

PCV = Pre Command Variable		Delta T = Tcabin - Tdesired Cabin (Non linearized)									
		40	25	10	5	0	-5	-10	-25	-40	
T Ambient	40	-100	-100	-70	-40	-20	0	10	30	100	
	25	-100	-90	-60	-20	-5	10	20	50	100	
	10	-100	-80	-40	-15	5	20	35	60	100	
	5	-100	-70	-30	-10	10	25	40	70	100	
	0	-100	-60	-20	-5	15	30	55	80	100	
	-5	-100	-50	-10	0	25	40	70	90	100	
	-10	-100	-40	-5	10	35	55	80	100	100	
	-20	-100	-30	0	20	40	70	90	100	100	

CV = Command Variable		PCV = Pre Command Variable									
		-100	-70	-40	-20	0	20	40	70	100	
T Cabin Interface	28	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	26	40	20	40	60	80	80	80	90	100	
	24	0	-20	0	20	40	50	60	80	100	
	22	-100	-70	-40	-20	0	20	40	70	100	
	20	-100	-80	-60	-50	-40	-20	0	20	40	
	18	-100	-90	-80	-80	-80	-60	-40	-20	0	
	16	-100	-100	-100	-100	-100	-100	-100	-100	-100	

Figure 14: Evaluation Matrix

4.1.1 State Machine

The control strategy is contingent upon the system state, necessitating a state machine to facilitate transitions between these states. The state machine delineates states, conditions for state transitions, and actions executed within the selected states, or the control strategy applied to the actuators. Figure 15 illustrates the state machine's encompassing nine distinct states. The first level selection which is done by the state machine is between cooling, heating

and reheat. The critical condition for transitioning between cooling and heating is the CV value. Transitioning to reheat modes is triggered by the cabin humidity.

The cooling modes are divided into passive cooling and active cooling, with active cooling being initiated at elevated ambient temperatures. In heating mode, the cabin is consistently heated via the heat pump function of the refrigerant circuit. These modes primarily differ based on the HV-battery temperature. At lower HV-battery temperatures, the HV-battery is actively heated. As the temperature increases, the HV-battery operates in a recirculation mode until the waste heat from the HV-battery can be utilized as a heat source for the heat pump. If the temperature escalates excessively, the HV-battery undergoes passive cooling.

Reheat modes are activated when cabin humidity surpasses a predetermined threshold. During these modes, the supply air to the cabin is initially cooled and subsequently reheated to a target value. This cooling process achieves maximum water saturation in the air, resulting in the separation of liquid water. Post-heating at the outlet, the absolute humidity is reduced compared to the inlet. In reheat mode, the cabin is predominantly heated. The modes vary based on the HV-battery temperature, with the HV-battery being either heated, cooled, or operating in an isolated recirculation mode.

Figure 15: State Machine Logic

4.1.1.1 Heating Mode

During the heating mode the refrigerant circuit is running in heat pump mode. Traction battery and cabin are both heated. The heat pump draws its heating energy by a radiator from the ambient air. This is limited by the ambient air temperature. Further heating is achieved via an additional positive temperature coefficient (PTC) e-heater with can be activated. The powertrain is running in an isolated recirculation mode. The active parts are highlighted in Figure 16.

Refrigerant Circuit:

In heating mode, the refrigerant circuit heats the HT-circuit using heat pump functionality. Heat is extracted from the LT-circuit in the chiller and released into the HT-circuit via the iCond. Both the cabin and the HV-battery are heated with the HT-circuit. The TXV_2 (valve) is closed, and the TXV_1 (valve) controls the superheat after the chiller. In the compressor, the temperature and pressure of the refrigerant increases. The iCond functions as a condenser, heating the coolant in the HT-circuit. Pressure and temperature of the refrigerant are reduced in the active TXV_1. The chiller acts as an evaporator, absorbing heat from the coolant in the LT-circuit.

Coolant Circuit:

The HV-battery is heated via the HT circuit (valves 10, 4, 5 and 9). Valve 5 is controlling the inlet volume flow rate into the HV-battery circuit which leads to a target inlet temperature, while the other valves are at a fixed position (V10=100, V4=0, V9=100). Heat is added to the circuit via iCond and the e-heater (PTC). The LT-circuit serves as heat source for the refrigerant circuit. In the chiller the coolant is cooled down a few degrees. The coolant reaches the components first and then reaches the radiator. The coolant is heated up from the ambient air. The MT-circuit is running in an isolated mode until the target temperature is reached. The coolant flows through the e-machine to the water heat exchanger which is not active back to the pump.

Figure 16: Heating Battery and Cabin with the Ambient Air as Heat Source

4.1.1.2 Cooling Mode

In cooling mode, the evaporator is used to cool down the cabin supply air. Traction battery and HT-circuit are connected for passive cooling of the components, which means that the waste heat of the system is transferred from the coolant to the ambient air by the radiator package.

The waste heat of the powertrain components is also transferred to the air in the Radiator 3. The active parts are highlighted in Figure 17.

Refrigerant Circuit:

In cooling mode, the refrigerant circuit is used to cool down the supply air to the cabin. The TXV_1 is closed, and the TXV_2 is controlling the superheat after the evaporator. Before the compressor the refrigerant is gaseous and at a low temperature and pressure. In the compressor electric energy is used to increase the temperature and pressure of the refrigerant. This gaseous refrigerant is entering the iCond at a high pressure and temperature. The refrigerant is condensing on the walls of the iCond which are cooled by the coolant. Heat is transferred from the refrigerant to the coolant in the HT-circuit. The liquid refrigerant is collected in the accumulator. After the outlet of the accumulator the refrigerant is entering the TXV_2. When the refrigerant is going through that throttle this will cause a sudden drop in pressure, which leads to lower temperature. In the evaporator that cold refrigerant is absorbing heat, from the supply air to the cabin, and will be evaporating during that process before it enters the compressor again.

Figure 17: Active Cooling for Cabin and passive cooling for the Battery

Coolant Circuit:

The HV-battery and HT-circuit are connected. The heat sources in the circuits are the iCond and HV-battery. The heated-up coolant is cooled down in the radiator 1 and 2. The LT-circuit is not active. In the MT-circuit the coolant absorbs waste heat from the e-machine. Valve 7 directs the coolant volume flow through the radiator 3 where the heat will be released to the airflow. The water heat exchanger is not active in this mode.

4.1.1.3 Demisting mode

The reheat mode is used for the dehumidification of the supply air to the cabin. By dehumidifying the air, fogging of the vehicle windows is prevented. The Bat-circuit is running in an isolated mode and the MT-circuit is cooled by the ambient air. The active parts are highlighted in Figure 18.

Refrigerant Circuit:

The refrigerant circuit is running in the same mode as shown in chapter 4.1.1.2.

Coolant Circuit:

The Bat-circuit is running in an isolated mode. In the MT-circuit the waste heat from the e-machine is released to the ambient via the Radiator 3. The HT-circuit is also running in a small circuit. The coolant is only flowing through the iCond, E-Heater, Cabin-Heater, V2 and P2. The waste heat from the refrigerant circuit released to the coolant circuit in the iCond is used to heat up the supply air in the cabin heater, which was cooled down in the evaporator. If additional heat is needed the e-heater can be activated.

Figure 18: Reheat Mode for the Cabin and Battery in Recirculation Mode

4.1.1.4 Operation Modes/ Thermal Strategies

A variable architecture of the thermal management system enables high flexibility and diverse configuration possibilities. The primary goal of this architecture is to maximize efficiency and comfort. Based on these principles, various configurations and operating states have been developed.

Wherever possible, residual energy from the drivetrain and the HV-battery is used for heating. If this energy is insufficient, a heat pump is activated. When the heat pump exceeds its operational limits, an electric heater is engaged. For cooling, passive cooling is primarily used, utilizing ambient air through a radiator. Only the fan and circulation pumps consume electricity

in this process. If passive cooling is inadequate, the heat pump is activated to generate cooling energy. Table 6 outlines all operating states embedded in the thermal system.

Table 5: Overview of the Operation Modes

Mode	Description	Refrigerant circuit (RC)	HT circuit (HT)	MT circuit (MT)	LT circuit (LT)	Cabin (C)	Battery circuit (BC)
Case 1 (Heating)	HT battery and cabin heating incl. waste heat	RC heating ->HT	HT heat+PTC, waste heat->>C, BC	waste heat -->LT	radiator heat+BC-MT->RC	HT-->heating	BC -->LT
Case 2 (Heating)	HT Cabin heat up+ battery self-heat up	RC heating -->HT	HT heat+PTC-->C	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	radiator heat-->RC	HT-->heating	self-heat up (recirculation)
Case 3 (Heating)	HT battery and HT cabin heating	RC heating -->HT	HT heat+PTC-->C, BC	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	radiator heat-->RC	HT-->heating	HT -->heating
Case 4 (Heating)	LT battery and HT cabin heating incl. waste heat	RC heating -->HT	HT heat+PTC, waste heat->>C	waste heat -->LT	radiator heat-->RC, BC	HT-->heating	LT-->heating
Case 5 (Cooling)	LT/HT Battery + RC Cabin Cooling	RC cooling-->Cabin	LT/HT-->Radiator	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	LT/HT cooling-->BC	RC-->cooling	LT/HT radiator->radiator
Case 6 (Cooling)	LT Battery + RC Cabin Cooling	RC cooling-->Cabin+LT	HT-->Radiator	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	LT cooling-->BC	RC-->cooling	BC cooling->RC
Case 7 (Defogging/Defemisting (Reheat) 1)	Defogging/Defemisting (Reheat) Cabin + battery self-heat up	RC heating-->HT	HT-->Cabin	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	hold	HT-->heating	self-heat up (recirculation)
Case 8 (Defogging/Defemisting (Reheat))	Defogging/Defemisting (Reheat) Cabin + battery heating	RC heating-->HT RC cooling Cabin	HT-->Cabin, BC	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	hold	HT-->heating	HT-->heating
Case 9 (Defogging/Defemisting (Reheat))	Defogging/Defemisting (Reheat) Cabin + battery cooling	RC heating-->HT RC cooling ->BC	HT-->Cabin	waste heat -->radiator/ambience	hold	HT-->heating	RC-->cooling

The thermal management can be set flexibly and according to the specifications or the thermal operating ranges. The same applies to the cabin air conditioning. The strategies and the thermal operating limits which are currently used for control can be found in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Thermal Management System

		Ambient Temperature			
		Cold - -20°C	Moderate Cold - 0°C	Standard - 23°C	Hot - 40°C
Battery cell temperature / E-drive temperature	Cold - 20°C	Battery is connected to HT circuit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> up to 3°C avg cell temperature, battery is actively heated with e-heater Flow is depending on dT of the battery → Mode 3 (Battery heating)			POWERTRAIN THERMAL MANAGEMENT DRIVING
	Mode rate Cold 0°C	Heat Pump <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat pump usage is possible depending on coolant temperature with e-drive or/and battery via chiller. → Mode 1 (Heating with waste heat)	Battery is isolated or connected to LT circuit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Between 3 ° - 12 °C avg cell temperature, battery is isolated and heating up itself → Mode 2 (WP ambient, isolated Bat)		
	Standard 23°C	Powertrain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is running isolated. Waste heat can be given to the ambient via radiator and valve 7 or to the LT circuit via heat exchanger and valve 6. 	Heat Pump <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat pump is possible depending on coolant temperature with e-drive or/and battery via chiller. → Mode 1 (Heating with waste heat)	Battery cooling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the cooling modes the battery will be cooled passive for avg cell temperatures below 32 °C. → Mode 5 (Passive Bat cooling)	
	Hot 40°C		Powertrain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is running isolated. Waste heat can be given to the ambient via Radiator and valve 7 or to the LT circuit via heat exchanger and valve 6. 	Powertrain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is running isolated. Waste heat can be given to the ambient via Radiator and valve 7 or to the LT circuit via heat exchanger and valve 6. 	Battery cooling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For higher avg cell temperature and in high load driving battery can be cooled active with the chiller. → Mode 6 (Active Bat cooling)

Figure 19: Thermal Strategy for the Thermal Management System

Cabin

		Ambient Temperature			
		Cold - -20°C	Moderate Cold - 0°C	Standard - 23°C	Hot - 40°C
Battery cell temperature / E-drive temperature	Cold - 20°C	Cabin heating is done via e-heater in the HT circuit through the cabin heater → Mode 1-4 No heat pump with ambient at very low ambient temperature → Mode 2 (Heating ambient)			THERMAL MANAGEMENT CABIN COMFORT
	Mode rate Cold 0°C	Heat pump with e-drive and/or battery via chiller is active when coolant temperature is above 15°C. → Mode 1 (Heating with waste heat)	Cabin heating is done via e-heater in the HT circuit through the cabin heater → Mode 1-4 Cabin heating via heat pump functionality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste heat from e-drive and/or battery used via chiller. → Mode 1 (Heating with waste heat)		
	Standard 23°C	Reheat mode for low temperatures unlikely, depending on cabin humidity → Mode 7-9 (Reheat)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is operated via the coolant radiator with intense fan activation. → Mode 2 (Heating with ambient)	E-heater usage is not restricted to a specific mode, but the intensity can be limited for each mode.	
	Hot 40°C				Cabin cooling suffers hot ambient temperature. When battery cooling requirement is high, cabin conditioning is turned off for the limited cooling capabilities of the refrigerant circuit.

Figure 20: Thermal Strategy for the Cabin

4.1.2 Control Algorithm for Actuators

4.1.2.1 Actuators (Cooling Circuits)

The control of the actuators in the cooling circuit is adapted to the requirements of the components. In a self-developed control toolbox, some standard controllers, such as constant blocks, characteristic maps, and proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers, are available for selection. For the PID controllers, it can be further distinguished whether they are state-dependent or not and whether the setpoints are specified by a signal or a parameter. Additionally, the input and output values can be limited or manipulated depending on the state. For each actuator, up to 5 control elements can be selected in the standard configuration. An example is shown for the pump in the MT-circuit in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Structure of the Control Algorithm for the MT Pump

In this example, state-dependent PID controllers are used. The first controller receives the setpoint for the temperature difference dT (15 K) between the inlet and outlet temperature in the power electronics as the target value. The four other options are not assigned. The output signals of all possible controllers are connected in a max block. Thus, the maximum value from the controllers is passed on to the actuator. This max connection can be adapted depending on the actuator and requirements. For safety-relevant functions, this can also be replaced or adapted by a min connection.

Another approach is shown for V4 in Figure 22. This valve controls the flow into the LT-circuit to cool or heat up the HV-battery. The control algorithm consists of a binary controller and a PID controller with an external input for the setpoint. The binary controller can only decide state-dependently whether the valve is open or closed. With the external PID, the coolant inlet temperature into the HV-battery is regulated. The maximum value from both controllers is output to the actuator.

Figure 22: Structure of the Control Algorithm for the V4 valve

In general, the strategy was followed that a temperature difference at the components is represented with the pumps. The setpoint inlet temperature is regulated with the valves. The fan in the radiator package is activated when certain temperatures are exceeded. For the blower, the cabin temperature is mainly relevant. The air distribution into the cabin is determined by the mode, and the other air flaps are regulated to a desired temperature after the evaporator or cabin heater.

4.1.2.2 Actuators (Refrigerant Circuit)

The structure of the refrigeration circuit (R1234yf) was described in chapter 3.1.2.1. The actuator to be controlled is the compressor since there is no controller needed for the TXV valves. In total the control strategy of the compressor consists out of five variants of PID controllers. Three of them try to control the target temperature and two of them are for safety reasons to control the minimum and maximum of the allowed pressure in the refrigerant. In this case all the outputs of the controllers are connected to a min block which only allows the minimum output signal to go to the actuator.

Figure 23: Structure of the Control Algorithm for the compressor 1

4.2 Controller-based Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) (Sutton, 2018) is a ML paradigm, in which an agent¹ learns to make decisions by interacting with its environment, aiming to maximize cumulative rewards over time. This framework is particularly suited to complex, dynamic systems where optimal actions are not predefined but need to be discovered through trial and error. In recent years, RL has gained traction as a promising alternative to traditional engineering controllers, particularly in domains like EV) thermal management. Unlike conventional control systems, which rely on pre-designed control laws and fixed operating conditions, RL adapts in real-time to a range of environmental conditions and usage patterns. This adaptability is especially beneficial for managing energy-efficiency and cabin heating demands in EVs, where operational conditions vary significantly due to weather, driving habits, and HV-battery state. By continuously learning and optimizing energy use in response to these dynamic factors, RL-based controllers can improve energy-efficiency and passenger comfort beyond the capabilities of traditional thermal management solutions.

Several studies (Ganesh, 2022) have already extensively explored and employed a wide range of RL algorithms to optimize thermal management scenarios in EVs, demonstrating promising results in terms of both energy-efficiency and passenger comfort. Li et al. (Li, 2024) proposed a RL framework that utilizes a double deep Q-learning algorithm to address the high energy consumption required to maintain cabin temperature in cold climates. The study illustrates how RL can dynamically balance the heating needs of the cabin with the vehicle's overall energy consumption, reducing HV-battery drain while maintaining a comfortable cabin environment. Recently, Dai et al. (Dai, 2024) developed and evaluated several RL algorithms

¹ An artificial intelligence (AI) agent refers to a system or program that is capable of autonomously performing tasks on behalf of a user or another system by designing its workflow and using available tools.

by incorporating environmental factors, such as solar radiation intensity. Results showed that Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) algorithm achieved better performance in the variation in average rewards, which demonstrates its excellent adaptability to different external environments.

4.2.1 RL Training Environment

The two main components of an RL model are defined by the **training agent** and the **environment**. The environment contains all information required for calculating the training target, which includes an executable digital twin of the plant (the **control law**), a list of actions that can be performed (by **control actuators**), as well as use-case specific information on the control targets (called **control set trajectory** and **constraints**). The agent is implemented as an algorithm that optimizes the control policy for a given reward model. The thermal control optimization environment of SmartCorners will be set up to comply with:

- Flexibility in the co-simulation platform
- Independence of the exact plant model
- Support of multiple RL libraries and training algorithms
- Incorporation of user-preferences during training (efficiency vs. accuracy trade-off)
- Large control structures with pre-defined topologies

Figure 25 shows the overview of all components of the RL training environment of the thermal control optimization environment.

Figure 24: Components Overview of the Thermal Control Optimization Environment

4.2.2 RL Components

Plant & Controller Models:

The plant model constitutes the main component of the environment for the RL agent to interact with. It calculates signals relevant for the reward function, particularly the temperature at distinct locations in the cabin and the energy consumption during a cycle.

The main requirement for the plant model is that the agent can continuously interact with the simulation, i.e., changing plant input values and reading plant output values during cycle execution. It is also required that the simulation's execution can be scaled and performed on remote clusters using Linux operating systems. For this reason, it was decided that the preferred plant interface was the FMI standard, since this interface allows the agent to execute

the co-simulation on various platforms. Moreover, the fact that the simulation can be executed in the same process as the training agent allows for efficient and stable training. Nevertheless, plant interfaces to other tools (such as the ICOS interface to AVL Model.CONNECT) could be used during the project.

The default controller model is required for evaluating the performance of the trained controller model versus an established benchmark model and for extracting a sparse ML topology for the policy network.

Data Model:

The data model contains all necessary information about the cycle conditions under which the controller model shall be executed during training. The generated scenarios used for AI training must include all relevant operating conditions, w.r.t:

- Various drive cycles
- Operating conditions (radiation, humidity, ambient temperature)
- User preferences (e.g. heart rate information using smart sensors)

Reward Model:

The reward model defines all optimization targets and constraints which are considered during training. This component is a critical component for RL since it defines how to trade-of conflicting goals and optimization constraints, such as:

- Target trajectory accuracy (cooling/heating set targets)
- Energy-efficiency
- User preferences
- Operating constraints (hard limits)

These targets for model training should be easily adaptable for the user, e.g., using yaml parameter files.

RL Training:

The training environment should be kept as generic as possible to allow for different controller training algorithms to be used. Specifically, algorithms from two open-source python libraries will be used for training, namely:

- Ray RLlib
- SB3 (stable-baselines3)

Since in practical applications the controller models can be complex, the thermal control optimization environment will allow the user to pre-define a control topology. This allows the user to easily restrict the number of parameters in the controller model. Sparse policy networks take less time to train and are less likely to overfit during training. The default controller model will be used to define an initial ML topology.

4.2.3 AI Controller Structure

The controller structure depicted in Figure 26 consists of two parts: a generic, non-AI-based controller, and an AI-based controller. The non-AI-based controller is usually a rule-based

state-machine, which can switch between different operating modes and the actuators can be controlled by PID-type control mechanisms. The AI-based controller is seen as a complementary controller in parallel to the existing rule-based controller. Its main advantage is that it can be trained in an automated fashion using RL, which means that the AI-based layer can be refined for each user individually according to the user's preferences.

Figure 25: Control Structure: Parallel AI-based & non-AI-based controllers

4.3 Predictive Models

One key advantage of using AI-based control strategies is that these methods can optimize the strategy by predicting future loads and operating conditions. For example, pre-conditioned vehicles can operate more efficiently both with respect to energy consumption and user's preferences.

Several predictive models can be used for predicting operating conditions, such as:

- Scheduled/rule-based drive cycles
- Learned schedules from previous behaviour or calendar information
- Weather predictions
- Smart sensors (biometric data, acoustic sensors, ...)

During the project it will be assessed under which circumstances – particularly w.r.t. the prediction accuracy of these models - and to which extent these load predictions can improve controller performance.

5 Conclusion

This report presents a comprehensive description of the design process of the vehicle thermal management and HVAC systems. An analysis of modern thermal systems was carried out and state-of-the-art attributes were evaluated. The thermal performance, energy-efficiency, environmental impact, performance under extreme conditions, user comfort and convenience functions, technological features and control, cost and maintenance and safety of thermal systems currently on the market were derived.

The design of the thermal system requires high performance and innovative solutions to remain competitive. To select the right thermal management system for the SmartCorners project. Thermal systems of vehicles currently on the market were evaluated. A state-of-the-art thermal system was derived from this. This was compared with the architecture of the thermal system of the demo vehicle to ensure that this system has all modern functions and is suitable for use in the project. The system was declared suitable.

This was followed by a detailed analysis of the demo vehicle system's architecture, both hardware and software has been done. State-of-the-art thermal management control software relies on techniques based on manually designed control strategies and tuning of PID controllers. However, modern control strategies are expected to become more complex in the future, as the current control strategies do not take individual passenger preferences or predicted driving profiles and weather conditions into account. AI control strategies will be developed in the scope of the SmartCorners project, whereby ML-models assist the available control state-machines in evaluating the optimal actuator demand values during operation. The ML-training can be automated for each customer individually using telemetric driving data (using RL). Since RL training is computationally complex, detailed, and fast surrogate models for the cabin and the HVAC system are required.

The thermal model as well as the cabin model will be used to train the AI-supported thermal control system before using it in the vehicle. For this reason, further improvement of the cabin model was mandatory. A new method was developed to optimize the model's capabilities in relation to 3D resolution of the cabin flow and comfort evaluation. The model development is still in progress. It will represent a great asset for further project progress for the training of the RL.

AI or RL shows enormous potential to significantly improve the efficiency of highly dynamic systems such as thermal and HVAC systems for vehicles. In Task 3.1, a methodology for implementing RL was developed to improve the actuator control as a first step. ML approaches are crucial in quickly adapting the system to the constantly changing thermal boundary condition and improving efficiency and comfort at the same time.

All in all, the SmartCorners project will show significant progress in thermal management and passenger comfort and paves the way for future developments in EV design with integrated RL approaches. The integration of predictive models and AI controllers further improves the performance of the system and ensures a robust and adaptive thermal management solution.

5.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

This deliverable is delayed by two months to perform the set out review by the project steering board for public release.

6 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long text
3D	Three dimensional
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BC	Battery circuit
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
C	Cabin
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CR	Comfort Rating
CV	Command Variable
DDPG	Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
EHT	Equivalent homogeneous temperature
EV	Electric vehicle
FRM	Fast Running Model
hmi	human machine interface
HP	Heat pump
HT	High-Temperature
HV	High-voltage
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICOND	Internal Condenser
K	Kelvin
LT	Low-Temperature
ML	Machine learning
MT	Medium-Temperature
PCV	Pre Command Variable
PID-Controller	Proportional–integral–derivative Controller
\dot{Q}	The heat flux
PMV	Predicted mean vote
PPD	Predicted percentage of dissatisfied
PTC	Positive temperature coefficient

R1234yf	Refrigerant type
RC	Refrigerant circuit
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SB3	stable-baselines 3
TXV	Thermostatic expansion valve
T_s	Skin temperature
WP	Work Package
x_0, x_1	Constants

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